

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for MDH1 (UniProt ID: P40925) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

Malate dehydrogenase 1 is an enzyme crucial for regulating cellular metabolism. It is responsible for the conversion of malate to oxaloacetate, facilitating the regulation of energy balance between the cytoplasm and mitochondria. Here we have characterized thirteen MDH1 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P40925, *MDH1*, MDH1, Malate dehydrogenase 1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The malate dehydrogenase 1 protein, named MDH1 here, is encoded by the *MDH1* gene and contains a Rossmann-like domain essential for binding the NAD⁺ or NADH cofactors as well as a catalytic malate dehydrogenase domain. MDH1 is an enzyme that catalyzes the reversible conversion of malate to oxaloacetate using NAD⁺ as a cofactor, playing a crucial role in maintaining energy balance between the cytoplasm and mitochondria and in the tricarboxylic acid cycle of the mitochondrial matrix (1). In cancer cells, disruption of MDH1 function is often associated with poor prognosis (2).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (3). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (3). Here we characterized thirteen commercial MDH1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of MDH1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (4) and in Table 3 of this data note (3).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (5, 6). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than 2.5 log₂ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (7). The HAP1 cell line expresses the *MDH1* transcript at 8.3 log₂ TPM+1. A *MDH1* KO HAP1 cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1).

To screen the thirteen antibodies by western blot, WT and *MDH1* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all thirteen antibodies MDH1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of the thirteen antibodies to capture MDH1 from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a

specific MDH1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, the thirteen antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the MDH1 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (3).

In conclusion, we have screened thirteen MDH1 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (7). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect MDH1 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study MDH1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available MDH1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in MDH1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. MDH1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, the same antibody clones are donated by 2-3 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (3). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (8, 9).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR001 and RGAM001, respectively. CoraLite Plus-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR003 and RGAM003, respectively. Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary MDH1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (10). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability*Underlying data*

Zenodo: Dataset for the MDH1 antibody screening study <[10.5281/zenodo.17401419](https://zenodo.org/record/17401419)>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC007264c008	CVCL_XQ35	HAP1	<i>MDH1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the MDH1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab180152**	1022435-10	NA	recombinant mono	EPR13597(B)	rabbit	0.12	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab181091**	1070141-2	NA	recombinant mono	EPR13596(B)	rabbit	0.52	Wb
ABclonal	A7563	0037750201	AB_2768088	polyclonal	-	rabbit	3.31	Wb
ABclonal	A9673**	4000001692	AB_2863757	recombinant mono	ARC1692	rabbit	0.16	Wb
Abnova	H00004190-M01*	P3041-S3	AB_2143283	monoclonal	2B11-B7	mouse	1.00	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP48284_T100	QC19448-90910	AB_1294489	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-32582**	H651815021	NA	recombinant mono	JE35-03	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	CPTC-MDH1-1*	5/30/19	AB_10805146	monoclonal	CPTC-MDH1-1	mouse	0.03	Wb
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	CPTC-MDH1-3*	2/13/20	AB_10805425	monoclonal	CPTC-MDH1-3	mouse	0.03	Wb
GeneTex	GTX130900	42291	AB_2886380	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.95	Wb,
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38200**	AC4650223B	AB_2898117	recombinant mono	ARC1692	rabbit	0.16	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-56543**	AC4649685C	AB_3679570	recombinant mono	JE35-03	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-57454**	AC4649694A	AB_3680479	recombinant mono	24GB1295	rabbit	0.16	Wb

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT	WT	WT	SM	SM	SM	KO	KO	KO
KO	KO	KO	UB	UB	UB			
IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	IP			
kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa			
245-	245-	245-	245-	245-	245-			
135-	135-	135-	135-	135-	135-			
75-	75-	75-	75-	75-	75-			
48-	48-	48-	48-	48-	48-			
25-	25-	25-	25-	25-	25-			
11-	11-	11-	11-	11-	11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP	Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected	

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Figure 1: MDH1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: MDH1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: MDH1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: MDH1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO were prepared, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated MDH1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab180152** at 1/10 000, ab181091** at 1/1000, A7563 at 1/1000, A9673** at 1/1000, H00004190-M01* at 1/1000, ARP48284_T100 at 1/250 (2.5 µg/mL), NBP3-32582** at 1/1000, CPTC-MDH1-1* at 1/68 (0.5 µg/mL), CPTC-MDH1-3* at 1/63, GTX130900 at 1/500, MA5-38200** at 1/1000, MA5-56543** at 1/1000, and MA5-57454** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 36.4 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: MDH1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated MDH1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the MDH1 antibody ab180152** used at 1/10 000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, HC= antibody heavy chain. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: MDH1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *MDH1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated MDH1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab180152** at 1/100, ab181091** at 1/250, A7563 at 1/1000, A9673** at 1/75, H00004190-M01* at 1/500, ARP48284_T100 at 1/500, NBP3-32582** at 1/500, CPTC-MDH1-1* at 1/500, CPTC-MDH1-3* at 1/500, GTX130900 at 1/1500, MA5-38200** at 1/75, MA5-56543** at 1/100, MA5-57454** at 1/75. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.